

SPECIAL SCHOOL VISIT REPORT

MAH E UROOJ (29327)

Department of Education, Iqra University

M.Phil (Education)

Dr. Anjum Bano Kazmi

EDU611: Emerging Issues In Education In Pakistan

January 15, 2025

Table of Contents

➤ Introduction:.....	3
➤ Objective of the visit:	3
➤ Attendees/Interviewees:	3
➤ Summary of Activities/Observations:.....	3
➤ Detailed Observations:.....	5
➤ Al-Shifa Strategy:	5
➤ Al-Shifa Special School and Rehabilitation Centre Photo Gallery:.....	6
➤ Issues/Concerns Identified:.....	11
➤ Recommendations:.....	11

➤ **Introduction:**

The report outlines my visit to the Al-Shifa Trust Special School and Rehabilitation Centre situated at Terminal-2 Road, Karachi Airport, Karachi-75200. This charitable institute was formed in 1967 through the collaboration of PIA and Civil Aviation. In 1981, it was converted into a Trust.

➤ **Objective of the visit:**

The objectives of the educational visit were as follows:

- i. Institute role in catering to the needs of a special student.
- ii. General problems of these students.
- iii. General problems faced by the teachers in classroom management.

➤ **Attendees/Interviewees:**

- I. Incharge: Mr. Shoaib.
- II. Headmistress: Ms. Tanveer.
- III. Co-ordinator.
- IV. Speech therapist.
- V. Physiotherapist.
- VI. Special schoolteachers.

➤ **Summary of Activities/Observations:**

❖ **Knowledge-based learning:**

- English, Urdu, Mathematics, General knowledge (Islamiat and General Science)

❖ **Skill-based learning:**

- Cognitive.

- Fine gross.
- Social.
- Self-help.
- Language.

❖ **Extra-curricular activities:**

- Tableaus.
- PTM.
- Functions.
- Educational trips: Rangoonwala.
- Picnic.
- Games: Special Olympic Pakistan.
- Arts competition.

❖ **Offered services:**

- Physiotherapy.
- Speech therapy.
- Hydrotherapy.
- Conductive education.
- Occupational therapy.
- Orthoses and Prostheses.
- Orthopedic and Pediatric OPD.
- Sports activities.
- Music class.

➤ **Detailed Observations:**

Al-Shifa Trust is a beacon of light and hope for those special children suffering due to negligence and lack of facilities. This institute aim is to bring these special children back to life and not only educate but also equip them with skills to lead an independent lively life. During my visit I interviewed the Headmistress regarding the Al-Shifa facilitation. Some of my personal observation is mentioned below:

- Admission criteria 4-12 years old.
- Medical aids available.
- Wheelchair accessible area.
- School classes: Montessori-Grade 3.
- Affiliated special schools after grade 3.
- Neat and clean classrooms.
- Well-organized classrooms.
- Qualified head and staff.
- Separate play area.
- Skill-based vocational training: Computer training, Artwork. Stitching, cooking and beautician course.

➤ **Al-Shifa Strategy:**

To provide medical facility to children suffering from:

- Cerebral palsy.
- Down syndrome.

Children mental and physical health assessment is made by a team of medical doctor such as orthopedic surgeon, physiotherapist, and a pediatrician. A well-planned therapeutic treatment and curriculum designed to cater to the needs of every special admitted child.

➤ **Al-Shifa Special School and Rehabilitation Centre Photo Gallery:**

Al-Shifa Special school Headmistress: Ms. Tanveer

Coordinator

Al-Shifa entrance gate

➤ **Issues/Concerns Identified:**

Some of the key issues identified during my educational visit at Al-Shifa special school are highlighted below:

- Governmental budget constraints.
- Inadequacy of federal funding and financial aid.
- Limited assistive devices or technology such as braille textbooks, a screen reader, a sign language interpreter, or a captioning service etc.

➤ **Recommendations:**

Following steps must be taken to ensure a safe and inclusive special education system:

- 1) Special school education recruitment programs.
- 2) Parental counselling.
- 3) Governmental support.
- 4) Provision of special health medical aid and facility.
- 5) Maximize the number of special treatment at medical facilities.